

D 5.1

Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (APRE)

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Clean Hydrogen Partnership. Neither the European Union nor the Clean Hydrogen Partnership can be held responsible for them.

www.hypop-project.eu

info@hypop-project.eu

#HYPOPPROJECT

D 5.1	Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
DELIVERABLE TYPE	Report
MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERABLE	M3, 08/09/2023
WORK PACKAGE	WP 5
LEADER	Lead Beneficiary
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public
AUTHORS	Marco Regi Chiara Pocaterra Sara Silvi
PROGRAMME	HORIZON EUROPE
GRANT AGREEMENT	101111933
START	01/Jun/2023
DURATION	24 Months

Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Marco Regi	APRE
Chiara Pocaterra	APRE
Sara Silvi	APRE

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Marianna Franchino	ENVI
Ilaria Schiavi	ENVI

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	COMMENTS
0.1	15/07/2023	Marco Regi (APRE), Sara Silvi (APRE), Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)	first draft
0.2	01/08/2023	Marianna Franchino (ENVI) Marco Regi (APRE)	Review of first draft version
0.3	31/08/2023	Marco Regi (APRE), Sara Silvi (APRE), Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)	Second review (first document issue – Deliverable D5.1)

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union, neither the European Union Institutions and Bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Deliverable abstract

The present document D5.1 Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan is the first deliverable of Work Package 5 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation. This deliverable intends to present an overall strategy dedicated to awareness raising about HYPOP: based on the defined objectives and making use of the communication and dissemination tools developed, it aims at addressing the relevant target audiences identified and promoting the project and its results. The report also identifies the expected exploitable assets and prepares the exploitation of the project results. This document specifies also responsibilities and metrics set to ensure a swift implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

Keywords

Dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, outreach, awareness raising, communication toolkit, target group, exploitable asset, result, impact

Index of Contents

1	Introduction.....	8
1.1.	Context and background	8
1.2.	Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP.....	9
2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of project results	11
3	HYPOP Communication and Dissemination Strategy	13
3.1	Project vision and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy	13
3.2	Target Groups, Stakeholders, Audience, and Key Message	14
3.3	Dissemination channels including Communication Tools	19
3.3.1	Project branding and toolkit.....	20
3.3.2	Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer	21
3.3.3	Dissemination channels making use of communication tool.....	22
3.4	Planning of the dissemination activities	22
3.5	Partner's rule in communication and dissemination.....	23
3.6	Communication and Dissemination monitoring.....	25
4	HYPOP Exploitation Strategy	30
4.1	Introduction & Objectives	30
4.2	HYPOP key end-users.....	30
4.2.1	Experts from research/academia	30
4.2.2	Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations.....	31
4.2.3	EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions, innovation agencies	31
4.2.4	Other initiatives and projects based on thematic and methodological interest.....	31
4.2.5	Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)	32
4.3	Planning of exploitation	32
4.3.1	Steps for reach HYPOP's objectives	33
5	Conclusions.....	34
6	Annex 1 – Dissemination channels making use of communication tools	35
7	Annex 2 – Concept note for events organised by HYPOP's Partner	41
8	References	43

Index of Tables

Table 1 - HYPOP's Target Groups.....	16
Table 2 - HYPOP's Target Groups initial KPI	17
Table 3 - Citizen and Stakeholders involved	19
Table 4 - Project's KPIs for Dissemination and Communication and related activities.....	28
Table 5 - HYPOP LinkedIn profile overview	37

Index of Figures

Figure 1 - HYPOP's Target Groups	17
Figure 2 - HYPOP logo and baseline	21
Figure 3 - HYPOP visual ID color codes	21
Figure 4 - HYPOP Word template	21
Figure 5 - Steps necessary to reach the HYPOP's objectives	33

Partners short names

ENVI	Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional De Experimentacione de Tecnologias De Hidrogeno Y Pilasde Combustible Consorcio
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodородen Klaster

Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement

Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are of paramount importance to the success and impact of project HYPOP – HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance.

HYPOP shall make use of the EU H2020 and Horizon Europe projects' dissemination and communication best practices and follow the 6W approach: What, Why, When, hoW, Where and to Whom to disseminate / to communicate.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a reference document for strategically and effectively disseminating knowledge and information throughout the project. This document aims to go a step further than what was described in HYPOP's Documents (Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement), in terms of what should be done to ensure effective dissemination about the project and its outcomes. It also defines the target audiences for communication and dissemination in more details.

Communication and dissemination are key levers to maximise the impact of the project. They are nevertheless two different concepts. Communication is about increasing the visibility of the project, while dissemination is about preparing the ground for the exploitation of the project results. In this communication and dissemination plan, both activities will be addressed: an initial plan for dissemination of results will be presented to bring forward the dissemination activities which are instrumental to the exploitation of results of the project; it will make use of channels and tools that are also used for communication matters. The present Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan will be further updated at M12 of the project.

In addition, this report provides a first Exploitation Plan for the use of project results.

This deliverable is also a guide for project partners on how to promote the project and maximise its impact using the right promotional tools and dissemination channels, engaging stakeholders through targeted messages, adequate channels and ensuring thus an impactful engagement of them (in line with the Stakeholder Engagement strategy of the project).

This document further indicates the roles and responsibilities of the partners related to communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

1 Introduction

1.1. Context and background

Project HYPOP - HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance, Grant Agreement nr 101111933 is a project supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, and co-funded by the European Union.

Project HYPOP's Overall Objective is to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through:

- the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of Hydrogen technologies
- the creation of a web platform, and social media, collecting communication material, mainly videos, on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities.

To reach the overall goals of the project, 2 different target groups will be targeted, engaged and involved directly in dedicated activities:

- the first target group brings together: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyze the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes the following stakeholders: First responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies.

The development of Hydrogen technologies and their integration into the market energy can represent an important opportunity to face the challenge of climate neutrality and the energy crisis that Europe, its economy and its citizens are currently living through.

Public awareness activities are essential for increasing social acceptance and trust in hydrogen-based technologies throughout the European Union, particularly for addressing the potential lack of knowledge or mistrust of key stakeholders directly involved in the first phases of mass deployment in Europe.

This Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation aims at outlining an adequate and impactful approach towards awareness raising and outreach, supporting thus strongly the engagement of relevant stakeholders in the project activity and preparing the ground for the use of its results.

1.2. Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP

HYPOP will strive to achieve the following specific objectives:

- Understanding public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies
- Identification of the main individual-level determinants of public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technologies
- Enhancing involvement of citizens in the implementation of solutions contributing to the transition to hydrogen and fuel cells
- Understanding the pathways to influence public opinion by analysis of the current depiction of hydrogen technologies in broadcasts, newspapers, and social media, and from this developing a public information strategy
- Assessment of the specific role of the socio-economic and environmental impacts of hydrogen technologies
- Clear guidance on safety and certification and support to obtain permits and authorisations for installing hydrogen technologies
- Engagement on Hydrogen Technologies' implementation
- Identifying the safety approaches and the safety barriers in a range of different Countries, in order to create a map of the main requirements (certification) for installing hydrogen technologies and facilities
- Identifying the attitudes of the different countries towards social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) of the hydrogen technologies

Through its different operational activities, HYPOP will aim to achieve the objectives mentioned above, whilst the transversal work of “impact maximisation”, which includes communication and dissemination, will act in support: the aim being to **leverage results and bring them to an upper level, reaching the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders and engaging them into the project activities (in line with the stakeholder engagement strategy of the project) and the exploitation of results.**

Below the main project outcomes and expected impacts:

- Outcomes:
 - Reach a deeper comprehension of the public opinion on hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the social awareness, trust and reduction of the social distance to the hydrogen topic
 - Improvement of the understanding of the hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the scientific community and stakeholders' awareness of the public opinion on hydrogen topic, limits and possible drivers into the acceptance process
- Impacts:
 - Socio-cultural (increase the knowledge and acceptance)
 - Environmental/Climatic (hydrogen is a valid energy carrier used to produce clean energy with environment benefits)

- Scientific (create more efficient technologies to integrate into the market)
- Political (improvement and acceptance of the energy strategy proposed to address the challenges of reaching climate neutrality and mitigating the energy crisis in Europe)
- Economic (long-term benefits in terms of infrastructure, and energy supply at small and large scale).

2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of project results

Communication and Dissemination are essential to the success and impact of HYPOP objectives, its expected results and impacts.

Continuously sharing internal and external information is a transversal element that should be strategically and effectively conducted by partners throughout the project by taking into consideration all communities relevant for and interested in the project.

Hence, the current report first evokes HYPOP's objectives and expected outcomes and defines its key stakeholder and target audiences and the related key messages addressed to them. It further describes partners' roles and responsibilities when it comes to communication and dissemination activities, and the relevant processes and procedures to follow to ensure a smooth implementation and monitoring of such activities. The second part of the deliverable describes the Exploitation Strategy of HYPOP, identifying key exploitable assets and a pathway for their use.

What is the difference between communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of Horizon Europe¹?

Communication means informing, promoting and communicating on the project, its activities and results reaching out to multiple audiences (citizens, the media, etc.). Communication therefore requires having a well-designed strategy, conveying clear messages, and using the right communication channels from the very start of the project and until its end.

Dissemination is about making the results of the project public and available to all stakeholders who can learn about and possibly be interested in using them. Such stakeholders can include, but are not limited to, public authorities, industry, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society etc. Dissemination can translate into the publication of project results in scientific magazines, scientific or targeted conferences and events, and databases.

Exploitation is about making use of project results for commercial, societal and/or political purposes and impacts. Exploitation of results can be performed by researchers, industry, and generally all stakeholders that can make use of them including public authorities, industrial authorities, policymakers, civil society etc. Exploitation activities need to be driven by a roadmap. They take place usually towards the end of the project and beyond but can be implemented as soon as the project has produced exploitable results.

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation are closely intertwined. Communication and dissemination can make use of the same tools and channels while addressing different audiences for different matters. Dissemination prepares the use, i.e., the future exploitation of project results as it raises awareness among key target groups, which might later become involved in the exploitation paths of certain project results. This report therefore describes elements which can address at least two of these aspects at the same time, while making clear what the distinguishing elements are.

¹<https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/Communication%2C%20Dissemination%20and%20%20Exploitation-2021.pdf>

The proposed dissemination and communications strategies will follow a 6W approach to ensure that every dissemination opportunity is adequately exploited during and by the project. The 6W strategy aims to clearly identify:

- **Why to communicate and disseminate:** For efficient communication and dissemination activities, the first point to be identified are the objectives of the communication and dissemination;
- **To Whom to communicate and disseminate:** Different communication and dissemination objectives will have to target different audiences; these different audiences have to be defined;
- **What to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences have different interests and needs and will need to be addressed with different key messages defined according to the expected outcomes and impacts of the project;
- **hoW to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences (Industries, Research Centers, Accademia, SME, Citizens, etc.) have to be reached and addressed through different channels. To be efficient, communication and dissemination activities must be well-coordinated and monitored;
- **Where to communicate and disseminate:** To fully reach its objectives, the project has to communicate and disseminate to all its target audiences and all over Europe; and
- **When to communicate and disseminate:** The project communication and dissemination both must run throughout the duration of the project, with long lasting and scheduled actions, and take advantage of opportunities that may arise during the project.

3 HYPOP Communication and Dissemination Strategy

3.1 Project vision and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy

To produce a coherent and efficient communication and dissemination strategy, the first question to be answered is **Why should we communicate and disseminate? What are the communication and dissemination objectives of the project?**

Public awareness activities are essential for increasing social acceptance and trust in hydrogen-based technologies throughout the European Union, particularly for addressing the potential lack of knowledge or mistrust of key stakeholders directly involved in the first phases of mass deployment in Europe.

If the Communication is an activity mainly dedicated to inform about the project's vision, objectives, strategic relevance and key elements, the Dissemination aims to promote the project's results, such as guidelines, toolboxes and requirement analysis among hydrogen key actors and others stakeholders groups. Dissemination of knowledge and project achievements is a crucial part of HYPOP activities. In order to provide the ground for future initiatives and activities, it is important to raise awareness about the activities of HYPOP and present its results to relevant players: notably experts from research/academia and industry, Innovation agencies, Civil Society Stakeholders (CSS), associations representing society and consumers, businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs) as tech adopters/providers, policy makers, government institutions, other initiatives/projects, end-users and associations communities of practices.

In particular the above players and general categories will be specified in a dedicated HYPOP's Target Groups analysis (as per HYPOP Grant Agreement).

The overarching goals of the HYPOP communication and dissemination plan are to:

- maximise the visibility of the project, activities and objectives
- raise awareness among representatives of key stakeholder groups and support their engagement in project activities
- prepare and support the potential use of project results, and
- enhance synergies of the project by establishing relationships between the HYPOP project and other initiatives, networks, focusing on hydrogen technologies, identifying networking opportunities and possible synergies.

The communication activities support also the following:

- raising awareness about EU expertise and leadership in Hydrogen Technologies
- supporting acceptance by society and industry uptake, as well as expansion across ecosystems.

3.2 Target Groups, Stakeholders, Audience, and Key Message

The communication and dissemination strategy of the project answers to different needs and objectives, and therefore different audiences will be targeted. It is essential that different communities are addressed with messages and tools adapted to their interests and uses. This section answers the “**to Whom to communicate and disseminate**” and “**What to communicate and disseminate**” questions.

During the first months of the project, the partners will develop a map of Target Groups, Citizen/Stakeholders who could be involved in project’s engagement activities or could be interested in project’s results.

Results coming from the public understanding of hydrogen and fuel cell technologies SoA analysis (WP1), as well as from citizens’ and stakeholders’ engagement activities (WP3&WP4) will be used for the update of this document planned at M12. Inputs from the entire Consortium will be also useful.

The map will ensure that engagement activities involve a broad and balanced audience, including minorities, youth and the elder generation from urban, peri-urban and rural areas. For each identified target group APRE, as WP5 leader, will define their “stake” based on two key variables of interest and potential impact. This first branding and awareness raising activity will address all stakeholder groups.

The key messages highlighted during these first months shall include:

- What is the project about and what is its expected impact?
- What are the project objectives?
- Who is involved in the project?
- Which main activities are planned? Which results are expected?
- Who is addressed by the project/who can benefit from its activities and results, and how?

The messages listed above should be addressed through all promotional channels, such as the HYPOP website, social media, etc. For detailed information about these publication channels, please refer to the Annex 1.

Specific and dedicated activities will be organized by HYPOP’s Partners. In this case a dedicated format (in annex 2) will be completed and sent to APRE and ENVI for approval and related planning.

Other messages that will also be relevant and create dissemination opportunities as the project develops are:

- Public deliverables and Milestones achieved.

The principal EU Country involved in these activities are:

- Italy
- Ireland
- Spain
- Belgium
- Poland
- Bulgaria
- France
- Germany
- Netherland
- Switzerland.

A specific focus will be dedicated to EU funded projects:

- This subtask aims at maximizing the HYPOP project's impacts through the networking with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, starting from the ones in which partners are involved (e.g., GREEN HYSLAND, 2Ports, EVERYWH2ERE, HyLAW, BEST4Hy, eGHOSTandSH2).
- APRE in collaboration with the project partners, will map all the relevant projects and initiative (clustering) and will contact all the stakeholders to establish a collaboration on the project's activities.
- The collaboration will exploit synergies in terms of joint dissemination activities (e.g., joint organisation of workshops and events) and knowledge exchange to increase the uptake and replication potential of the project's outputs across Europe and beyond.
- The newly funded projects under HORIZON EUROPE (in the 2022 and 2023) calls will be also mapped and contacted.
- Demo project: some interviews will be performed, in order to identify weaknesses, barriers, criticality in Hydrogen Technologies implementation/certification and related acceptance by society.

All the above activities will be performed with the support of website, social media, YouTube channel.

In particular:

The website will inform stakeholders about the project and provide access to its main outputs. Social media accounts will provide a channel to reach target groups, promote the project, disseminate its results and raise awareness about hydrogen. The project will also leverage partners' social media accounts and websites, which have a solid number of local and international followers.

The HYPOP Team is aware that this kind of project activities typically are addressed to a dedicated audience. However, at the same time the use of hydrogen technologies very much depends on the acceptance by society and citizen (together with the industry uptake). This is why the project has foreseen many channels and tools that can address these different audiences, and specific emphasis is given to the type of information shared, as well as the style of communications – adapted to the audience. Therefore, in order to reach a Hydrogen Technologies society and citizen acceptance, dedicated initiatives will be performed with the support of specific analysis useful to define the best practices for the abovementioned acceptance.

HYPOP'S TARGET GROUPS

HYPOP's Teams will engage specific Target Groups:

- the first target group brings together: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyse the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes the following stakeholders: First responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

The above Target Groups will be better defined by the analysis performed in WP1 (as per Grant Agreement) and WP2.

Three (3) minimum Target Groups for each Partner's Country will be reached.

In particular, the Target Groups will include:

Target Groups	Description
Citizens	Samples from 6 countries with different hydrogen social acceptance, different age, gender and sociocultural background. The analysis conducted will also integrate other states not HYPOP partners
Manufacturers/Hydrogen sector	providers and industries representatives from FCH technologies, specifically focus on residential, energy and transport sectors (synergies with other projects).
HYPOP identified stakeholders	first responders (at least from HYPOP 6 Countries), Permitting's entities (at least from HYPOP 6 Countries), Certification Body (AENOR as AB, at least 3 others)
Public authorities /decision-makers	local, regional and national decision-makers (10 minimum)
EU and local projects	European/not European projects (10), focused on hydrogen research and its application.
Clusters, territorial associations, networks, hydrogen valley	organizations working at territorial level and gathering figures from the same sectors (HYPOP project: ENVI, CNH2, RIGP. Tweed, BH2C + at least 5 territorial associations as H2IT and at least 3 Hydrogen Valley) or interested to create collaboration and enhance the local community growth
Experts on Hydrogen and Communication	technical or other figures working in hydrogen development projects, internal figures in the project or experts in communication (journalists, social media managers, press)
Scientific community	experts and scientist on hydrogen technologies, social aspects and technological innovation

Table 1 - HYPOP's Target Groups

Figure 1 - HYPOP's Target Groups

The table below illustrates an initial KPIs summary according to the GA (n° 101111933) and according to the JU Annual Work Programme and Strategic Research and Innovation Action (https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/knowledge-management/strategy-map-and-key-performance-indicators/clean-hydrogen-ju-sria-key-performance-indicators-kpis_en)

	TARGET Group	KPI per country	KPI tot (6 country overall)
1	HYPOP STAKEHOLDER - first responder	al least 1	6
2	Permitting Entities	al least 1	6
3	H2 Valley	al least 1	5
4	Education and Public Awareness	al least 3 (as per subtask 5.1.1 and related project team survey)	6
5	Citizen	specific 1 champion (with different hydrogen social acceptance, different age, gender and sociocultural background)	6
6	Certification bodies	ANOE and at least another 3 entities	4

Table 2 - HYPOP's Target Groups initial KPI

Target Groups' interests will be assessed with respect to the project objectives and incentives and benefits that can drive their engagement will be identified (more specific information will be part of the D1.1 and D4.1).

CITIZEN AND STAKEHOLDERS

HYPOP's Teams will engage (WP3 and WP4) specific Citizen and Stakeholder categories (see table below).

Citizen and Stakeholder categories	Key engagement	HYPOP Hub - Web Platform	Social Media	Expert Forum	Planned Events	Publication Repository	Workshops (co creation) Webinars	EU Technology pathway	Video/Infographics	Other Communication
Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)	Acceptance of citizens is needed for a technology uptake. CSOS will reinforce representativeness of their sectors/thematic focus for the benefit their members	X	X		X		X		X	
Experts from research/academia	HYPOP will increase the hydrogen technologies visibility through promotion in experts' webinars, workshop, conference, podcasts, etc., and to increase knowledge-sharing with and between these stakeholders	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations	These stakeholders will give first-end information on hydrogen technologies as they are early adopters/up-takers of new emerging technologies	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EU, national and regional policy bodies,	Public authorities and specifically									

governmental institutions, innovation agencies	decision makers of hydrogen technologies will be continuously targeted to be informed and familiarized with the concepts of enabling technologies	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Other initiatives and projects	These stakeholders contribute to community building through cross-pollination and fertilization in order to increase synergies and networks	X	X			X			X	X

Table 3 - Citizen and Stakeholders involved

3.3 Dissemination channels including Communication Tools

As presented in the above section, different target audiences have different uses and interests and must therefore be addressed by a complementary set of tools. This section presents the tools set-up for the project communication and dissemination as it further answers to the “**hoW** to communicate and disseminate” and “**What** to communicate and disseminate” questions.

Publications by HYPOP will aim at consolidating information about goals, activities and results of the project and motivate the relevant communities to provide feedback, communicate their requirements and get involved in relevant activities.

Most tools and channels for dissemination including communication are generated during the first six months of the HYPOP project.

The majority of this work is focused on the creation of media which will be maintained and used throughout the project as vehicles to disseminate and communicate information about the project and its achievements.

The envisaged communication and dissemination tools and channels will be:

- the HYPOP website (available from M4)
- HYPOP social media channels: LinkedIn, X (formerly known as Twitter), YouTube, Instagram
- project news and communications published on the website and social media channels and press releases distributed by partners and their network
- project public presentation with a generic overview of HYPOP to be used in events
- project flyer giving an overview of the project objectives, main activities and expected results

- project roll-ups/posters/banner
- project videos and infographics
- project publications, developed through the operational activities
- project co-creation workshops with experts
- project conferences, workshop and public events
- project webinars to support the promotion of experts knowledge and the Hydrogen Technology pathways' implementation
- engagement with initiatives and networks in the field of hydrogen, both at the European and international levels
- participation in major external events and conferences of interest, and
- information and knowledge exchange with and through other relevant initiatives for the exploitation of synergies.

3.3.1 Project branding and toolkit

During the first months of the project, the major activity related to dissemination including communication concerns the establishment of a project branding, i.e., recognition.

In this regard, HYPOP branding elements have been defined in order to make the project easily recognisable.

The branding elements have been gathered into a “communication toolkit” which shall represent the stable visual element for project presentation and promotion, and which includes the project logo and visual ID and templates (Word, PPT); a flyer, poster/roll-up and a generic project overview in PPT format will be added to it over time.

The toolkit has been prepared by APRE with the support of a professional designer and is to be used by all project partners.

The project logo has been designed by a professional designer. The logo has been designed to be easily recognisable and is composed of elements representing the core aspects of HYPOP: emerging enabling technologies.

A baseline can be added to specify the project aim.

The logo with baseline is as follows:

Figure 2 - HYPOP logo and baseline

Different versions of the HYPOP logo have been produced, adapted to different backgrounds and displays (screen, print, white background, etc.). The logo is available both in pixel and vector formats and is available for the partners' use via the project shared platform.

The visual identity is based on the main logo colours and should be respected in all official communication supports. The colour codes are as follows:

Figure 3 - HYPOP visual ID color codes

Based on the project logo and visual identity other branding elements have been developed:

- notably, a **graphical template for Word and PowerPoint**. This aims to ensure coherence and a professional level of quality in terms of design and presentation in all the project documents and communications.

Figure 4 - HYPOP Word template

- In addition, a **project banner** can be developed for the use on social media channels, as well as future use in events.

3.3.2 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer

As a beneficiary of support by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, one of the legal obligations of the project is to acknowledge the funding and display both the Clean Hydrogen Partnership logo and the EU emblem in all the communication material. Communication plays a key role in making the

public aware of the added value brought by combining private funds with European support to deliver high quality projects.

For this reason, every output of the project, including all communication material, must abide to the Clean Hydrogen Partnership Visual Identity Guidelines that can be found at https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/media/visual-identity_en and the EU branding policy that can be downloaded from https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en.

More specifically, the logos of both the Clean Hydrogen Partnership logo and the EU emblem with the text “co-funded by the European Union” must always be displayed. Both logos can be downloaded at the link reported above.

Furthermore, the following acknowledgment of funding must be displayed:

“The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members. Funded by the European Union”

This must be followed by the disclaimer

“Views and opinions expressed are however those of author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Clean Hydrogen Partnership. Neither the European Union nor the Clean Hydrogen Partnership can be held responsible for them.”

3.3.3 Dissemination channels making use of communication tool

HYPOP will use different types of communication tools throughout the project to effectively disseminate information, results, etc.:

- HYPOP Hub – web platform
- social media channels
- events and webinars
- videos
- infographics
- news, flyers brochures, posters, etc.

The details of those communication and dissemination tools are provided in Annex 1.

3.4 Planning of the dissemination activities

To ensure the dissemination strategy stays up to date, an internal planning, coordination and monitoring process shall be followed. In addition, all partners must report on their activities and opportunities.

APRE, as WP5 leader, will regularly check the progress and, if needed, adjust the planning of dissemination activities.

APRE will also supervise all activities and provide strategic direction when needed.

APRE will further coordinate the collection of updates and news content from partners in order to produce news on the project website and will handle the posts on social media pages.

A single 'Communication and Dissemination (C&D) planning and monitoring' Excel file will be developed by APRE used by all partners to **plan, coordinate and report** on all communication and dissemination activities, as well as on the preparation and publishing of news and social media posts. This Excel file will be reviewed regularly and updated by APRE with the support of consortium partners, indicating:

- actions
- person in charge
- channel to be used
- purpose of the action
- content to be conveyed
- targeted audience
- etc.

This file will also provide a monthly planning of communication and dissemination activities and actions to be taken, that will be constantly updated.

To ensure the timely reception of partners' contribution of news content, APRE will send reminder emails every month. In addition, WP6 activities will be discussed during consortium General Assembly meetings, and dedicated WP6 teleconference calls are set up to provide a platform to discuss any relevant issues.

Moreover, each event to be organised as part of the HYPOP project will be first defined and described in an event concept note. The template for the event concept note is available in Annex 2.

3.5 Partner's rule in communication and dissemination

To achieve the communication and dissemination objectives described above, concrete processes and procedures should be put in place for coordinating and implementing the dissemination strategy including communication. This section answers to the **"how to communicate and disseminate"** question.

To ensure and cross check the performance of the communication and dissemination activities against the strategic goals, it is necessary to nominate the responsible partners, to follow up the implementation of activities and to control the process.

More specifically, dissemination of the project and dissemination of knowledge gained during the project lifetime is expected to take place through the consortium members, their networks, the relevant HYPOP's initiatives.

In order to optimize the dissemination project activities, the following activities will be organized:

- definition of a dedicated Editorial Plan
- Each partner (as per the previous editorial plan) proposes a “news” to be published
- Each proposed news will be analysed by APRE and ENVI, suggesting integration/variation etc.
- “news” final version (as per a dedicated HYPOP Format) will be published and disseminated by all Partners using their respective media channels and all HYPOP’s communication channels (social media, you tube, etc.)

Partners have agreed on the roles regarding HYPOP’s dissemination including the following communication activities:

- The work package 5 is led by APRE.
- All partners will work closely with APRE to provide input to all the dissemination activities, therefore playing an important role in spreading information.

The work task responsibilities are distributed as follows:

APRE – Work Package leader:

Leads the management and coordination of the work package including:

- setting up of the communication and dissemination strategy
- monitoring and coordinating the dissemination and communication activities throughout Europe
- interacting with all partners for the dissemination and communication activities, and
- stimulating partners to provide dissemination input, such as news for publication on the project website, etc.
- drives the dissemination including communication activities
- provide text of relevant news and publications related to general project activities
- ensure quality control of the information provided
- creation of a visual identity and provision of templates (Logo, Word and PowerPoint)
- production of promotional material based on the contributions from partners
- set up and update of the project website
- prepare and organize the distribution of the press releases (disseminated by all partners through their channels)
- ensure the quality of the dissemination towards experts, and
- manage the HYPOP expert talks webinars, dialogue and contact with “external partner” (ex. Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory).

In particular, in order to optimize communication and dissemination activities (by social media, website, youtube, etc.), a specific dedicated *Editorial Plan* will be developed by APRE during the project activities.

The above Editorial Plan will be provided by APRE to all project Partners, in order to perform the following specific activities:

All Project Partners:

All Partners shall (using the Editorial Plan developed by APRE):

- use the project's visual identity for any disseminate on the project
- provide contributions/material for public use on the project website and communication material upon request (e.g., use case descriptions, logos, etc.)
- provide news and/or communications on important activities and achievements related to HYPOP
- inform APRE about possible participation in conferences, workshops, etc. related to HYPOP
- provide short texts about participation in events for the news section of the project website (accompanied by related links and pictures whenever available)
- disseminate HYPOP information, materials and deliverables through their channels and networks, notably in the format of newsletters, press communications, social media posts, etc
- regularly inform APRE about which communication channels and networks were used, and
- provide the required information for the reporting for the EC (see template in Excel sheet provided by separate mail to the partners).

The Partners will fulfil their responsibilities autonomously and provide input in time to all the dissemination and communication activities driven by APRE; but also, proactively disseminate information on the project activities and outcomes via their channels and networks. The entire consortium is playing an important role in disseminating information.

An update on communication and dissemination activities reported by the partners will be part of the agenda of the plenary meetings.

A list of dedicated communication/dissemination contacts within the project partners will be set up and is maintained by APRE.

3.6 Communication and Dissemination monitoring

Measurable targets and performance indicators are set for the dissemination work. Besides the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) listed in the table below, a number of project activities naturally feed into the dissemination work (activities conducted in the gap analysis, workshops, reports, etc.) The monitoring will be based on the expected outcomes specified in section 1.

#	KPI	Target	Audience
1	HYPOP's visual identity and related promotional	N. of brand identity kit released: 1 N. of social media banners: 2 N. of flyers: 2 N. of roll-ups: 2 N. of informative posters >2 N. of flyers distributed >2000	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large
2	Design infographics and develop informative videos	N. of informative videos to explain hydrogen and its application translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >3 N. of infographics to visualise project's outputs translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >5	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large
3	Website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, X, Instagram)	<u>Website:</u> N. of website online (M4): 1 N. of total visits: > 15.000 N. of countries reached >27 <u>Social media:</u> N. of accounts setup and active (M6): 4 N. of posts per year (total): >50 N. of social media campaigns: >5 <u>N. of LinkedIn//X followers:</u> Y1: n° 700 Y2: n° 1000	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large

#	KPI	Target	Audience
		<p><u>N. of Instagram followers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 1000</p> <p>Y2: n° 500</p> <p><u>YouTube viewers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 300</p> <p>Y2: n° 600</p> <p>N. of general local event per country participated by the local partner): >1</p> <p>N. of article/radio or tv interviews in national or regional media by local partners for each partner country: >1</p>	
4	Participation in external events and conferences and promotion through traditional media channels (*)	<p>N. of participation in events with dedicated booths: >3</p> <p>N. of speeches at events and conferences (live and online): >5</p> <p>N. of articles in newspapers, magazines or radio: >8</p> <p>N. of press releases (to 10.000 + contacts): >6</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>
6	Joint activities with other initiatives and networks	<p>N. of joint activities (expert meetings): 1</p> <p>N. of mutual learning workshop: >1</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers,</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience
		N. of online meetings with Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory: >3	community at large
		N. of online meetings with EU Clean Hydrogen Mission: >3	
7	Interconnection with hydrogen demo-project	N. of joint activities, demonstration event: 4	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large

Table 4 - Project's KPIs for Dissemination and Communication and related activities

(*):

Conference:

- <https://conferenceindex.org/conferences/hydrogen> (List of Hydrogen Conference 2023/2024/2025)
- <https://www.setac.org/discover-events/global-meetings.html> (SETAC Europe 35th Annual Meeting, expected in May 2025)
- <https://www.iahe.org/whewhwc.asp> (11th World Hydrogen Technology Convention, Dublin, 2025)
- <https://euhydrogenweek.eu/> (Hydrogen Week 2023/2024)
- <https://www.pollutec.com/en-gb/cometopollutecadwb.html> (POLLUTEC FAIR, Lyon, France, October 2023/2024, Participation with a booth this year)
- [H2 Day, organised by Environment Park once a year with its company cluster. Next one on 26th of October 2023](#)
- <https://www.ecomondo.com/> (ECOMONDO Fair (Rimini, Italy), once a year)
- <https://interactive.eusew.eu/> (EUSEW Brussels. Once a year)
- <https://hydrogen-uk.org/annual-conference-and-awards/> (11th,12th March - Hydrogen UK Annual Conference & Awards 2024)
- <https://www.whoecancun.org/tracks> (23th-27th June - World Hydrogen Energy Conference)
- <https://www.europe.gh2events.com/registration> (25th -27th June - Connecting Green Hydrogen Europe)
- https://waset.org/hydrogen-energy-and-fuel-cells-technology-conference-in-september-2024-in-malaga?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing (6th-7th September - ICHEFCT 2024: 18. International Conference on Hydrogen Energy and Fuel Cells Technology)
- https://waset.org/fuel-cells-hydrogen-energy-technology-and-applications-conference-in-december-2024-in-amsterdam?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing (2nd-3rd December - International Conference on Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Energy Technology and Applications)

Hydrogen Principal Scientific Journal, Specialised Magazine, local radio:

- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-hydrogen-energy>
- <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/hydrogen>
- <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2023/07/230713142013.htm>
- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-hydrogen-energy> (International Journal of Hydrogen Energy)
- <https://thehydrogenstandard.com/> (The Hydrogen Standards)
- <https://h2-international.com/> (H2 International)
- <https://revolve.media/magazine/> (REVOLVE Media magazine)

<https://www.ilsole24ore.com> (Il Sole24Ore)

<https://www.radio24.ilsole24ore.com> (Radio24 – Il Sole24Ore)

http://www.nuova-energia.com/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=44&Itemid=74 (Nuova Energia)

<https://www.rivistaenergia.it/la-rivista/> (Energia)

Local events:

<https://www.centroscienza.it/settimanedellascienza/> (Le Settimane della Scienza, Italy – Torino, every spring)

<https://www.nottedeiricercatori.it> (La Notte dei ricercatori, (Italy - Torino, International, every spring)

An update on the dissemination activities will be made during the consortium General Assembly meetings and all dissemination activities will be kept in the dedicated monitoring file for reporting purposes.

4 HYPOP Exploitation Strategy

4.1 Introduction & Objectives

Clean hydrogen is an energy vector used as fuel or for energy storage with technical and environmental advantages, due to its versatility, scalability, and, for green hydrogen, low carbon emissions.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies, in particular the Clean Energy package (Renewable Energy Directive REDII, REDIII1), the Green Deal, the European Hydrogen Strategy.

The transition to hydrogen and fuel cells is a long process that involves different stakeholders: policy- and decision-makers, technology providers, adopters, users and, last but not least, citizens. Understanding how the latter perceive hydrogen, together with a knowledge of the needs and barriers of technology providers and decision-makers, are fundamental elements to ensure a successful implementation of solutions for the transition in terms of policy, technical development and social awareness.

The HYPOP Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation (M1-24) activities will be discussed in WP5.

In this preliminary exploitation plan the consortium will be identifying (sub task n° 5.1.1: *Target Groups Map*):

- WHAT are the most relevant exploitable project results
- WHO will benefit from such results
- HOW will such results made available
- WHY it's important to make such results available.

4.2 HYPOP key end-users

The identified HYPOP's key end users are grouped using the following categories.

4.2.1 Experts from research/academia

Specific Categories: Scientific Communities

Scientists and researchers, digital, industrial and social technologist, intellectuals and academic educators, and other profiles connected to the academical and scientific community, are interested in the results and impact of HYPOP Project. They have multiple interest on HYPOP topics (hydrogen for transportation, heating, energy). They can use them for networking purposes, inspiration, information, new research lines identification, new development possibilities, knowledge transfer,

potential innovation projects as well as dissemination, reputation building, new areas specialisation, visibility and teaching materials.

4.2.2 Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations

Specific Categories: Hydrogen Technology Manufacturers and Provider

Industry and large companies as well as SMEs and entrepreneurs are interested in new trends, new legislation, norms and recommendations. Looking for information to be more competitive, sustainable and integrated into society. And, specially, be aware of the new legal requirements based on social and environmental impact conditions that are expected to be requested in next years (climate neutrality, clean energy production, green carbon free solution, etc.).

4.2.3 EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions, innovation agencies

Specific Categories: Decision maker, Public Authorities, EU and local projects, Experts on hydrogen technologies and communication

European Commission and other EU-level policy stakeholders have great interest to use Hydrogen assets to provide evidence and advise for new European Public Policies aimed to develop the competitiveness of Europe by integrating societal and environmental aspects (climate change, energy crisis, etc.) into technology development.

European strategies are followed by national, regional and local governments that, usually, try to be in line European Policies and strategies.

The target of the HYPOP project is to involves the following dedicated thematic networks:

- *National level: organization coordinating and representing hydrogen actors at the national level*
- *European level: European networks of actors involved in the development of hydrogen value chain*
- *International level: initiatives which link hydrogen networks and projects at the international level*

4.2.4 Other initiatives and projects based on thematic and methodological interest

Advisors, consultants and mentors as well as social and technological innovators are key-end-users.

They provide different types of services and vision related to the promotion, research, design, prototyping and validation, activation, dynamization and evaluation of technological pathways and future scenarios.

They allow the improvement and acceptance of the new energy strategy proposed to face and reach the challenges of climate neutrality and energy crisis in Europe, together with a change of citizens' perceptions for the proposed new energy solutions using Hydrogen Technologies.

Tailored exploitation activities will be included in a European-wide campaign aimed at raising awareness about hydrogen, promoting stakeholder engagement activities and enhancing the uptake of HYPOP's results.

In particular:

- engagement of the relevant Hydrogen Technologies Players and End Users
- define a project Brand identity that is consistent and easy to recognise, perceived positively by the different Target Groups
- provide dedicated materials (news, scientific papers, videos, etc.) useful to obtain the awareness about HYPOP's aims and objectives
- provide a better information about hydrogen and its applications, especially among young citizen, minority, etc.

4.2.5 Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)

Specific Categories: Citizens, Clusters, Territorial Associations, Networks, Hydrogen Communities

Professional associations, interest groups, the media, foundations, NGOs, cultural entities (with different age, gender and background), among others, may be interested in both the assets generated by the HYPOP project and the social, economical and environmental impacts that the introduction of hydrogen technologies entails.

These entities, in addition to exploring the potential social and green/ecological applications of hydrogen solutions, may also be interested in learning more about them to raise potential ethical and moral dilemmas such as transparency, open access to data, carbon free approach, new social inequalities, etc.

These debates have an impact on the media, on the Internet and on the cultural industries in general.

Important to include in the HYPO Project minorities, youth and elders with limited knowledge about hydrogen and related technological applications and solutions.

In particular is necessary to increase acceptance, knowledge and trust in hydrogen as clean energy source and valid technologies to use in different applications. Will be necessary to understand the effects of the climate change, energy crisis and the possible green solutions currently offered by the Hydrogen technologies available.

A significant opportunity for CSOS to have their voice heard will be the discussion on the indicators for the Social Life Cycle Assessment related to Hydrogen Technologies.

4.3 Planning of exploitation

The exploitation planning will ensure the following four objectives:

- support the project's engagement activities by reaching out target groups and promoting the initiatives
- ensure that project's outputs (such as guidelines, best practices and toolbox) are disseminated among the identified audience
- establish links and synergies with running projects and international initiatives in the field of FCH
- exploiting project's results beyond the end of the project, ensuring they are findable and accessible in the long term.

To optimize the HYPOP's results the best exploitation plane will be analysed, discussed and definite by the Project Team during the WP5 activities, and taking into account the interests and expectations of the stakeholders involved.

4.3.1 Steps for reach HYPOP's objectives

To reach the HYPOP's objectives, the following three steps has been individuated:

- Step 1:** Analysis
- Step 2:** Engagement/consultation of the Target Groups
- Step 3:** Results

Figure 5 - Steps necessary to reach the HYPOP's objectives

5 Conclusions

This deliverable provides a framework based on the 6W methodology to all consortium partners for promoting HYPOP's project activities and maximising their impacts through planned, coordinated and monitored dissemination activities including communication.

The deliverable also describes the roles and responsibilities of partners in this regard and further identifies the project target audiences and the key messages to be delivered to them.

While APRE is the leader of WP5, all project partners will be continuously involved in the communication and dissemination activities.

The communication and dissemination activities implemented will be reported through the official reporting at the end of each reporting period.

An update of this document will be delivered during the HYPOP's project activities.

6 Annex 1 – Dissemination channels making use of communication tools

HYPOP WEB PLATFORM

The first version of the HYPOP website will be available by the end of M3. It provides a responsive design in order to be correctly displayed on any type of device (ranging from regular PC to mobile devices).

The website represents the first vehicle in raising awareness of the project and contains a general presentation of the project objectives and the consortium, as well as all public information related to the project activities, results, events etc.

It will also give information to stakeholders about “How to get involved”, provide access to a Community Platform and an option to subscribe to the project newsletter, as well as share interesting reports publicly available and gathered through HYPOP which are deemed of interest to the stakeholders addressed.

The website will be accessible through the URL www.hypop-project.eu and follows the HYPOP branding and plays an important role in the information campaign. The content of the website will be updated continuously, e.g., whenever new information becomes available.

Promotion of the HYPOP project is also planned to be done through other relevant web portals in order to create synergy effects. Cross-promotion is planned notably through other Hydrogen projects links.

The project website addresses all targeted audiences of the project, including the general public. It will present a general introduction to the project and its potential impact even for an audience unfamiliar with the subject.

Visitors will find news of the project and access to publications, public deliverables, and events.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Great emphasis will be placed by the project team to create a HYPOP community consisting of people likely to be interested in implementations.

In this context, the project team will exploit the power of social networks and available internet tools in order to enable a more active communication and dissemination towards the community.

Specifically :

- HYPOP has already established profiles in professional social networks such as LinkedIn. This will be used as direct communication channel and to address

dissemination to other professionals from relevant fields: experts from academia and research, relevant initiatives, etc. Updates on events, news or advancement of the project will be published in the networks, with the aim to increase the awareness and finally the impact of HYPOP. Previous experience has shown LinkedIn as a good way to share information about events and publications and to reach a large audience.

- HYPOP has already started identifying the most appropriate social network communities (e.g. a broad and balanced audience, including minorities, youth and the elder generation from urban, peri-urban and rural areas). These communities are approached to attract their members and subsequently enrich the HYPOP community.
- In addition, a YouTube channel will be created when deemed necessary as a repository to support the dissemination of the future project videos.

LINKEDIN

HYPOP LinkedIn company page: (under construction)

LinkedIn is a professional network through which HYPOP can address very specific, professional target groups.

It is mainly functional for targeted networking and to create a sustainable network in which the status of the project but also project outcomes can be shared.

The main aim will be to constitute an interested community for hydrogen technologies.

The HYPOP profile was set up as a LinkedIn company profile, which seemed the best option to interact easily with existing other networks and exploit synergies with them. The profile will be filled with more details and content over the coming months, building more connections to people within the topic scope.

Objective	To announce HYPOP achievements to professionals from relevant fields of action, to raise awareness and questions and obtain feedback that can contribute to the project's development. Also announce events and gather interest from other people that join our community.
Content and Messages	Keep in contact and inform professionals; create a community
Target Audience	All Stakeholders and target groups
Information Required	Project updates, current news, discussions for receiving further feedback and suggestions on project's approach and results
Information Provider	All Partners
Activities	Encouraging new members to join, regularly adding new posts and responding to others' comments
Schedule	On a monthly basis, or as we have content to add

Monitoring	APRE is monitoring the company page as a minimum twice a month
Responsible Partner	APRE

Table 5 - HYPOP LinkedIn profile overview

X

X is an innovative and young-oriented social platform.

It allows and promotes further engagement of identified target groups through its interactive nature.

Thanks to X is possible to involve not only Hydrogen experts (researchers, managers, engineers, etc.) but also a significant number of citizen with a general interest to the hydrogen technologies and their social implementation.

Every day millions access to X are reached. Therefore, this social media is likely to allow to reach a significant number of visualizations of the HYPOP project activities.

INSTAGRAM

Instagram is a popular photo and video sharing social networking service.

It is a very suitable platform useful to reach a large popular audience (young in particular) with a possible general interest in hydrogen technologies.

No specific scientific topics will be discussed in this social platform, but is a useful instrument for a general project dissemination activity and for engagement.

General info (conference, news, info, etc.) will be posted to HYPOP Instagram page.

YOUTUBE

YouTube is a popular video sharing website where registered users can upload and share videos with anyone being able to view them, even without registering an account.

YouTube is an excellent platform to save project videos, in order to share them with a broad audience.

Targeted audiences will receive specific messages – through emailing, other social media channels, website news, in direct exchange – to invite them to watch the videos HYPOP will place on YouTube. As such, YouTube will be a “repository” platform for HYPOP.

The HYPOP’s YouTube account will be created once the first project video has been developed, likely to happen within the first project year.

In order to reach all potential stakeholders, a set of videos will be developed using the following criteria:

- provide a general and short HYPOP project presentation
- understanding of hydrogen: how the technology works, which are the benefits, climatic impacts, applications, etc.
- promote/highlight specific activities and results of the project (e.g., co-creation workshops, etc.)
- illustrates the results and impacts created by the project (e.g. citizen acceptance, etc.).

EVENTS

A number of project events, such as workshops, conferences, webinars events are planned in the frame of HYPOP, either online or as physical gatherings in order to allow the partners to meet on a regular basis and to exchange with the target groups, present project ideas and findings and collect feedback. They will also aim at a knowledge and information exchange with the key expert stakeholders.

These physical events shall, wherever possible and relevant, be organised in conjunction with a relevant external event (conference), in order to allow for synergies with the event participants and content.

- **Co - creation on line workshops**

Dedicated online public engagement co-creation workshops will be organized by HYPOP Team in order to involve citizens, specialist, researchers, etc.

The aim of the workshops will be to involve citizens in the project activities and topics.

In addition to informing about the project, the project team plan to ask participants to reflect on their hopes for hydrogen future aspects (use, green impacts, carbon free vision, etc.)

The planning foresees:

- one workshop per country (at least 20 participants per country, three-hour duration)
- two international events (at least 50 participants per event, one/two-hour duration).

Skilled facilitators will encourage group interactions to capture relevant data and to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the group discussions.

The rationale for having these workshops online is that it can be actioned at a lower cost than in-person events in different EU countries.

In particular, as indicated by GA (see the Project Summary Section), using also the results of the above events, the HYPOP Team will prepare the guidelines and the good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of the Hydrogen Technologies.

- **Stakeholders engagement workshop**

The aim of the workshops is inform and present, to the stakeholders, the main results related to the hydrogen acceptance requirements.

In particular, identifying for each Country:

- safety approaches and barriers
- certification rules
- regulation and standard procedures (hydrogen transportation, storage, use, etc.)

The final target is to create main requirements road maps in hydrogen technologies implementation.

The planning foresees:

- workshop (on line, 4 hours duration) per each project country
- final international event (in presence) near Clean Hydrogen Partnership headquarter (Brussels)

- **Outreach through other events**

In addition to the events organised by HYPOP, project partners will take the opportunity for communicating about the project developments towards specific/specialised stakeholders during events they organise in another frame or during external events they attend (international conference).

It is expected that partners will present the project, activities and outcomes in conferences they will be attending throughout the duration of the project, use the opportunities for awareness raising, making use of communication material such as the flyers, as well as creating connections and thus nourishing the HYPOP community over time.

PUBLICATION REPOSITORY

To promote the activities undertaken by the project (mapping, technology watch, engagement, dissemination, workshop, etc.), a complete publication repository shall be maintained on the project website.

It will contain:

- project press releases, videos, infographics
- promotional materials
- conference papers/presentations
- publicly available reports and analyses relevant for the HYPOP target group, and
- project publications and reports.

FLYERS & BROCHURES, Etc.

Flyers/brochures

A HYPOP flyer/brochure will be developed and used to present the project, its goals and the consortium. The project flyer shall reflect the ideas and planned activities of the project in a first step and might be updated with information about major outcomes and results in a second step, if deemed useful.

It shall serve as a calling card for presentations to influential stakeholders – experts, media representatives, etc. Produced early in the lifetime of a project, the first version of the flyer will:

- explain the background for undertaking the initiative
- indicate the targeted results, and
- provide an overview of the consortium and contacts: major contacts, website.

The flyer will be produced in pdf format, so it can also be used in electronic communications.

Banner/posters/roll-ups

For the use during events, it is also planned to develop one or several project banners (mainly virtual events or for the announcement of physical gatherings) and posters or roll-ups.

The posters/roll-ups will give a glimpse at the project aim and inform about major communication channels such as the website URL and social media accounts in order to allow anyone to get in touch with the HYPOP team easily and to find more information about the project.

The posters/roll-ups will be aligned with the project visual ID and take up major design elements already used for the templates and banners.

SINERGIES WITH OTHER HYDROGEN PROJECTS AND ORGANIZATIONS

To maximise both regional and EU-wide visibility and enhance long-term synergies, the HYPOP partners will actively work on establishing relationships with strategic EU actors.

In a dedicated HYPOP's WP5 subtask will be maximised the project's impacts through the networking with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, starting from the ones in which partners are involved (e.g., GREEN HYSLAND, H2Ports, EVERYWH2ERE, etc.). Furthermore, APRE will map all the relevant projects and initiatives (clustering) and will contact all the stakeholders to establish a collaboration on the project's activities.

Where possible synergies will also be created with organisations that have endorsed the project.

The overall aim of the networking and exchange around synergies will be to raise awareness within relevant target groups, to engage relevant actors into the project activities, and to serve common goals, broadening as such the impact of HYPOP and the initiatives it will be collaborating with.

7 Annex 2 – Concept note for events organised by HYPOP’s Partner

Concept Note for <Event Title>

Summary information of the event/activity (internal information)

Title of the event	E. g. HYPOP workshop “xxxx” (title)
Responsible Person	
Dates (Start-End) and duration	E.g. August 10 to August 12, 2023; 2 days in total
Location	E.g. Brussels, Belgium
Back-to-back event	Yes (if so, indicate) or no
Sectorial focus	Yes (if so, indicate) or no
Target Group	E.g. European researchers, policy makers from Member State ministries...
Indicative number of participants	E.g. maximum 20
Latest date when the public announcement should be published	At least 2 months before the event; give date DD.MM.YYYY
Specific additional dissemination channels	If any additional to the “usual” project channels
Main contributing partners and responsibilities	Indicate very briefly, to show who is involved

Planned associated partners/external org. to be involved	e.g. host : XX, trainers from X Y Z organisations
Work package	WPx
Contribution to sustainability of the project	Explain very briefly

Description of the proposed event (publishable)

Public announcement	Give 5-10 lines for web publication including title and ideally link to registration page or similar practical information
---------------------	--

Brief description of the event, if deemed useful to share (additional information to the public announcement above):

1. Aim and objectives:
2. Background and context:
3. Customer type (target group) (additional information to the public announcement above):
4. Application process, selection criteria:
5. Expected outcomes and impact:

Next Steps & Indicative Agenda (not published):

Concept agreed	When? DD.MM.YYYY
Event published	When? DD.MM.YYYY
Registration launched	When? DD.MM.YYYY
Participants informed	When? DD.MM.YYYY
Agenda fixed	
Logistics fixed	

Report:

Report due	E.g. +1 month after event
Report responsible	
Review responsible	E.g. contributing partners and/or associated partners
Report submission	Submission date to the coordinator DD.MM.YYYY
Report publication	Yes/No; if Yes date DD.MM.YYYY; if yes link to publication
Logistics fixed	

8 References

General Reference:

- GRANT AGREEMENT - Project: 101111933 – HYPOP – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2, 12/05/2023
- CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT - rev. 0, 13/03/2023

 www.hypop-project.eu

 info@hypop-project.eu

#HYPOPPROJECT

Let's make
the hydrogen
revolution

